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PROGRAMME: Luxury Brand Management Dissertation

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TITLE

**IMPLEMENTATION OF LUXURY HEALTH CARE AND ITS
INFLUENCE ON BOTH INDIVIDUALS AND HEALTHCARE
ORGANISATIONS**

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Abstract

The proportion of elderly adults living in care facilities has been increasing in the United Kingdom over the past few decades. This growth has led to growth of care facilities in the country. Further, more elderly adults have increasingly sought to merge the care they get in these facilities with their lifestyle. These factors have led to the emergence and growth of the luxury healthcare industry that merges personal care and human interaction. The existence of luxury care homes is based on individualized and personal care, which allows members of the care team to respond to requests promptly. The luxury healthcare market faces several challenges today. First, it has no distinctive model and is fragmented, leading to the absence of uniformity among existing homes. Further, the spread of COVID-19 has created vulnerabilities for care facilities, and patients alike. Therefore, there is a need to understand the state of the luxury healthcare market.

This study sought to understand the market, characteristics of its customers, and other environmental factors, to provide recommendations that enhance the delivery of luxury services to patients residing in luxury residential care facilities in the UK. The study was based on Veblen's Theory of the Leisure Class, which states that the purpose of luxury consumption is to display wealth and social status. The study used an interpretivist philosophy and an inductive approach to collect qualitative data through a literature review. The author found that the demand for luxury care homes is increasing with the decrease in the number of traditional care homes. Further, many patients are willing to pay a lot of money to access extra services provided by these facilities out-of-pocket as well as insurance covers that could cover most of the needs if not all. Furthermore, it was determined that the COVID-19 pandemic led to the growth of the market. Therefore, the author recommends that owners of such facilities invest more in them, as the luxury care homes market is expanding rapidly, with more people entering the retirement age.

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Acknowledgements

I would like to thank everyone who helped me write this thesis. First, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my family for standing beside me during the entire period of matriculation. Secondly, I would like to thank my mentors, who provided many useful suggestions that improved my writing and thesis.

Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Research Problem

The United Kingdom faces an exponentially growing elderly population considering an increase in life expectancy. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) state that approximately 20% of people aged 85 years and above in the United Kingdom live in care facilities, and most of them will die in those facilities. It is obvious that the growth in this segment of the population comes with an additional need for more care facilities in the country. At the same time, more people are looking towards merging their care with lifestyle. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) share that human contact is becoming a luxury good considering the increase in the contrast of personal care and human interaction. In this light, there is an increase in the need for more facilities that offer luxury care as more people in the UK are opting for such services.

As Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) note there is a need to improve end-of-life care, and the government should prioritise the issue by making sure that the palliative care practitioners and other staff provide comprehensive care to their patients. The government is not unaware of the need for increasing the availability of care for the aged and infirm. There are more regulations and improvements in standards to ensure that people receive care in a dignified manner. A care agency could be used to bring about changes in the concepts of care, patients' well-being and support them towards ensuring that they assume a lifestyle that tends to what they could achieve at their homes.

In most care agencies that run care homes, the facilities do not mostly align with the client's personal choices, as they handle all issues for the clients. For instance, some clients might want to do their own their cooking or do their shopping rather than have such processes done on their behalf. With the increasing demand for care agencies across the United Kingdom, more research must be done to understand what is needed to ensure that care agencies provide the services people expect and pay for and make such agencies more inclusive and focussed on providing the best possible care for the elderly.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought a whole new perception of care homes and care giving. Both the givers and receivers have been affected by the pandemic in various ways. COVID-19 and its consequent epidemiological control measures have led to diverse effects on care needs and care recipients worldwide. Caregivers and care recipients were exposed significantly, leading to unfathomed consequences relating to the control measures. The overall picture that emerges is that there needs to be in place a way to protect the two groups from contracting the disease from each other without compromising the service tasks. There is a need for interventions in care for the elderly population in order .to reduce the burden that arose as a result of the pandemic (Bergmann & Wagner, 2021). Additionally, there needs to be appropriate measures that ensure that the indicators of anxiety and depression in the givers and recipients of

care are enhanced. According to Bergmann and Wagner (2021), this is an issue that needs to be addressed by policymakers as well as social organisations, including elderly care homes. The use of a luxury facility that cares for the elderly should be set to promote the livelihoods of the affected population while also serving as a business opportunity.

During the spread of COVID-19, older people faced vulnerability and neglect. This challenge mainly affects institutions such as care homes. There are many reports of mistreatment and neglect of residents as caregivers scampered to escape contracting the virus. Further, older adults who are quarantined with family members may also be at risk of abuse, violence and neglect (United Nations, 2020). People living in risky conditions such as informal prisons and settlements and refugee camps face greater risk due to limited access to health care facilities and services, overcrowded settings, limited sanitation and water, and challenges of accessing assistance and humanitarian support. Older people in home-based care face more risks of exposure as caregivers do not spend all of their time in observing the protocols required to minimize the risk of contracting the virus. This is accurate since caregivers do not move in the patient's home but they spend periods of hours to several days at a time at the residence (Law et al., 2021). Again, caregivers operate in rotating shifts of twelve hours so the patient may be receiving care from different caregivers every day.

It is of note the majority of caregivers are women who care for other more senior people, especially in areas where long-term health care providers and health systems are weak (Law et al., 2021). The pandemic is also threatening older individuals' economic and social well-being and their access to jobs, pensions, and health care services. Individuals who receive care in the community and at home are also at the risk of being impacted by the social distancing procedures. Long-term periods of isolation could lead to mental health implications for older persons because they are less likely to be included in the digital world. Thus, social protection services can offer a safety net by providing older persons with pensions.

In line with providing better and improved palliative care in homes that cater for the elderly, this research focuses on making care agencies have a luxurious underpinning and seeks to look into the merits and demerits of having such care centres in the United Kingdom. Notably, the research stems from the need of having improved well-being and better health outcomes. A luxury care agency will focus on holistic care for the elderly while ensuring that the clients are in the best possible atmosphere that gives them a home feeling.

The care home market in the UK mainly provides care for individuals above 65 years. The market has no distinctive model and is fragmented; offering a diversity of businesses from cooperates that have hundreds to thousands of beds to sole businesses (Smith, 2018). Most of the homes are operated by charities and not for profit organisations. The largest providers make a small proportion of the market that has been dominated by the non-public independent players

for some time now. Traditionally, the homes are divided into those that provide nursing care and others that do not. While there is organic growth in the market, the existing homes do not have a uniform model. Notably, the upcoming homes have en-suite facilities and rooms that are more spacious. Most of the clients have their fees paid in part or entirely by local authorities. Notably, local authorities have shortness of funding considering that they pay an average of 10% less than the cost of care provision (Smith, 2018). As a result, self-paying individuals pay relatively high, with the average increase in their payments being at least 40% (Smith, 2018).

1.2 Research Aims and Objectives

The research aim of this study is:

- To evaluate the effectiveness of luxury care agencies in the UK.

This study aim at assessing the effectiveness of luxury care agencies in the UK. In addition, this study aims to offer some recommendations that could enhance the delivery of luxury services to patients residing luxury residential care in UK. These objectives focuses on understanding a market, the characteristics of its customers, and other environmental factors help in establishing an effective basis for improvement. The study aims at fulfilling several objectives necessary to enhance the luxury residential care in UK. These objectives include:

- To assess the attitudes that exist towards luxury care agencies by both consumers, the public and staff in luxury care home.
- The potential values/benefits that luxury care agencies have in the UK.
- How COVID-19 Coronavirus has resulted the growth of luxury care homes in UK?

There are several care agencies in the UK with luxury and premium services. Developing a profile of the market is critical to the transformation of the market and promoting the adoption of luxury services in long-term care. In turn, these objectives intend to evaluate the attitudes that exist towards luxury care agencies, which will aid in comprehending the merits of luxury care agencies in the region. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) indicate that luxury affects the perception of patients about the quality of palliative care. Luxury introduce a focus on the patient instead of focusing on the disease as the only subject. Hence, it is important to improve the nature of support offered to residents in care home and long-term care facilities. The gradual increase in demand for luxury services requires an analysis of the attitudes of care agencies and customers. In that manner, the study intends to offer in-depth insights into the implementation of luxury health care in UK and the way residents feel about this transformation.

Furthermore, the focus of this study involves assessing luxury care agencies by reviewing their effectiveness. Through this, the researcher will be in an excellent position to understand how successful are luxury care agencies are and the way UK residents have accepted these services.

Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) observes that luxury care needs has emerged as a desirable useful model to enhance the quality of life for the elderly. For that reason, it is important to develop an understanding of the nature of the market, perception of customers, and ideas on how to improve current services. Pertinent information about the market include data on the types of providers, target population, characteristics of customers, level of differentiation, and quality of providers. Palliative care and other long-term care services are established to promote the quality of life and end-of-life decisions by dying with dignity. More families and households have more income that enables them afford premium services. In addition, the research seeks establish the potential of luxury care agencies amid the need for more care because of the COVID-19 pandemic. Precisely, Coronavirus adversely affected people above the age of sixty five and those who had comorbidity. Most people above this age are struggling with one or more long-term condition requiring frequent monitoring emergency care. Nevertheless, this should be dine in an environment that does not have a substantial change on the livelihood of seniors.

In order to fulfil the stated objectives, the study focuses on information on relevant and related research questions. The study focus on discussing the effectiveness of the luxury care agencies in UK and its implication on residents. Residential homes are designed to meet the needs of a diverse market. The perspective of resident provide an objective view on the benefits of luxury services. The study intended to evaluate the attitudes of patient in care services and the characteristics of the current transformation.

In addition, the study evaluates the impact of luxury care agencies impacted the attitudes of consumers seeking medical help. The luxury care market is at its novel, which requires an understanding of the influence of care agencies on the attitudes of potential customers. The elderly requires constant attention, especially those with long-term conditions or those making end-of-life decisions. Residential homes should provide services that not only focus on treatment but also the lifestyle of its residents.

1.3 Outline of Methodology

The research process employed an interpretivism philosophy. According to Scauso (2020), interpretivism enables the exploration of novel strategies that luxury facilities in the UK may use to support the elderly in care. In essence, the author sought to look into the strategies that the facilities use in the provision of care. Additionally, the research will employ an inductive approach. An inductive approach, as Scauso (2020) notes, is an inductive approach allows the data to reproduce new meanings through the identification of various patterns as well as relationships in a data set.

The research methodology was qualitative in nature. Squires and Dorsen (2018) assert that qualitative research is essential in studying issues that entail regulations across all professions, including health and nursing. In essence, qualitative research is critical for espousing stakeholders' perspectives and ensuring that the views of relevant stakeholders are captured when implementing policy change (Squires and Dorsen, 2018). In this research, a qualitative method

was chosen since it could reveal human perceptions, opinions, actions and even experiences. McNab (2020) shares that a qualitative study enables a proper understanding of diverse human experiences in care.

Data will be collected from already existing current sources. The sources used were reputable since they offered a thorough, well-reasoned theory and discussion based on strong evidence. As a tool for data collection, the existing sources used contained information that matched the topic of interest. Notable sources used comprised peer reviewed journals that offered detailed information about the topic. Besides, the research involves the review of the recent literature with the aim of assessing, critiquing, and synthesising the research topic in a way that allows theoretical frameworks and methods to emerge.

Thematic analysis was the method of choice for analysing the collected data. A thematic analysis proved a feasible methodology since the researcher could use it to identify prevalent themes in the research that could lead to insights that answered the research questions. Besides, thematic analysis comprises three steps. The first step is analysing data involved initial reading and precoding. The second step involves the researcher going through the selected works in order to look for patterns and relationships. The final step is defining and naming the themes and reporting the analysis.

The author will ensure conformance to proper research ethics by formulating a valid and reliable methodology, pre-testing it and making the appropriate adjustments as needed to ensure that it conforms to all requirements. Since no humans will be ere to be interviewed, there is little danger of exposing anybody to data leakage. However, the researcher will ensure that the data collected is kept safe and will only be accessible to those who request it and that the institutions involved will be alerted well in advance to seek their permission. Again, all publications used in the review will be referenced appropriately. Any information from such sources will be reflected as accurately as possible to avoid distortions and make accurate conclusions.

1.4 Research Significance

The research is significant in that it contributes to diverse stakeholders in the ordinary care homes as well as giving an important insight in the potential for luxury care homes. In the first place, the research results will assist potential professionals in luxury care sector gain new insights and will highlight the potential and trends as they are currently. Moreover, the perception by many people is that care homes are a dreary and place for the aged and the infirm to receive palliative care as they wait to expire. This perception may be punctured or changed once the working of care homes and particularly luxury care homes is interrogated. This research

study highlights the perceptions of the population of luxury care homes as well as the feasibility of such care facilities in the United Kingdom.

Additionally, the research is significant for consumers, present and future. This is especially important to people who would want their loved ones to experience the best possible palliative care in their sunset days. In this light, the research will play an informative role in ensuring that such persons are aware of the aspects they would require their loved ones to experience. From the research findings, one can perceive the merits and demerits of luxury care facilities, and as such, serve as an essential source of information for potential users of luxury care homes.

The research contributes to the literature on luxury facilities in the United Kingdom in terms of improvement of care and also as a feasible business opportunity. Essentially, the research espouses the potential of luxury care facilities in the UK, thereby shedding some light on potential professionals as well as potential clients.

1.5 Dissertation Structure

The dissertation starts with an introduction that highlights the background to the research problem, the focus of the research, and how the researcher carried out the actual research. The section also contains the methodological choices, including the research design, data collection methods, and the methods of analysis. The second part of the dissertation looks at the literature review. Literature review includes a review of sources that based on the three hypothesised themes from the research questions. The literature review looked at the themes differently and as a combination of each other. From the literature review, what follow is the development of the research framework and a clarification of the research hypothesis. This is then, it is followed by a framework for the research and a clarification of the hypotheses a research propositions. The research methodology is the third chapter that includes an explanation and justification of the research philosophy, an explanation and justification of the research approach, an explanation and justification of the data collection procedures, an explanation of the data analysis procedures, and a statement indicating conformance to proper research ethics. The fourth chapter is the findings and presentation of the results. The section consists of the apparent themes in the research as well as the specific methods that the researcher applied in articulating the research findings. The fifth chapter is a discussion of the findings and results of the study. This section reports on the expected outcomes and what the research found in regard to the same. Also, the chapter links the findings to the review of literature, noting whether the results were linking to the literature and also reporting the unique contributions to literature. The last chapter is the conclusion and recommendation chapter which recaps the research objectives against the results. The chapter also indicates the implications of the research and any feasible contributions of the study. In addition, the chapter recommends further actions that could be taken in the field of luxury care, and lastly, the limitations of the current research process. The dissertation ends with a listing of all the sources as well as a list of appendices, including the log sheets, the ethical approval evidence, other approvals, and a brief reflection on the entire research process.

Chapter 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

When senior citizens face some illnesses, the family undergoes a daunting task in searching for the right care facility for the citizens. Care homes offering care for the elderly and also palliative care offer a good option for such members. There is increasing precedence and likelihood that most members will consider homes that offer the best facilities. In this light, some care centers are now providing luxurious care facilities to seniors.

2.1 Overview of the Chapter

This chapter reviews extant literature related to the study. In essence, the review is an essential process that generates ideas and diverse points of view regarding the topic of the research, connects research to theory, and gathers secondary information that will assist in expanding the researcher's knowledge regarding the subject. The current review focuses on the aim of the research, which are assessing the effectiveness of luxury care agencies in the United Kingdom and establishing the perceptions of people on luxury care agencies in the United Kingdom.

Importantly, this section is divided into key themes that tally with the research objectives. Before the actual analysis, a meaning of what luxury health care will be attempted and concluded. This will give the researcher a basis of determining what services constitute luxury and which do not. The review will then look at the three themes in unison. Further, the review will espouse the research framework, including the hypothesis of the research and end with a conclusion.

2.2 Luxury Care and Agencies in the United Kingdom

Luxury in care is subjective and can undergo several interpretations. Sudbury-Riley et al. (2019) notes that traditional concepts on luxury rest upon uniqueness, price, lack of necessity, comfort, quality and aesthetics. This is the traditional view held about what is luxury by many people. From the description, luxury was reserved for a privileged. Only a few as few could not afford luxury price wise it nor has the time or inclination to consume luxury. In contemporary times, the discussion on luxury has changed from the traditional ideologies to one that appreciates consumer experience as the novel unconventional luxury. In Sudbury-Riley et al.'s (2019) terms, the new approach to luxury is consumer-centered as opposed to market-centered. Expanding research is putting across experiential insights into the conceptualizations of luxury that illustrate meanings, states, moments, and experiences that consumers perceive for luxury. In hospice, luxury stems from the provision of customer-centric care by the agencies, leading to pleasurable, satisfying, positive experiences by the customers (Sudbury-Riley et al., 2019). Essentially, luxury in care is mostly about the experiences that the patients undergo in the care setting.

In the UK, care delivery to the aged and also to terminally ill patients is mostly done under hospice arrangement. In this regard, hospice-based care is delivered in various settings, including patients' homes, care homes, and special units across the various facilities (Sudbury-Riley et al., 2019). Hospice UK indicates that hospice services are free as they get funding from the government and charity. To access these services, one needs to go through some bureaucratic setups consisting of administrators, nurses, doctors, and other practitioners before care is received by those who need it. Through this setup, care is compromised, and patients do not necessarily receive the care they would desire to have.

There is potential for engaging luxury, especially in the rarely researched area of care. According to Sudbury-Riley et al. (2019), luxury is transitioning to experiential luxury in care homes. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) indicate luxury as the “moments of care” where such moments emanate from the experiences that consumers get from the personal interactions they have with the healthcare staff through authenticity in their presence, balancing of power relations, synchronizing their interpersonal relations. In this light, Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) state that luxury is evident in the humanity that showcases in the interpersonal interactions, surpassing material luxury. In addition, the authors indicate that such luxurious care needs establishment through a culture of care that aids the care managers, personnel, patients, and other representatives of the entire service industry.

2.3 Effectiveness of Luxury Care Homes in the United Kingdom

Notably, a few luxury care agencies or homes exist today. However, there is a very high potential for future growth given the expanding number of wealthy retirees and the increasing levels of awareness in the community (Stimpfel et al., 2020) about the merits of luxury care for invalids. . Considering the exponential growth of the healthcare industry across the globe, there is an increasing likelihood that care agencies will surge towards attracting more workers that will have better skills and be ready to provide the requisite care for the potential consumers. The increase in the number of the elderly across the developed world, and particularly in the United Kingdom is a positive indication of the rising trend in the demand for luxury care home (Halcomb et al. (2018). This trend is predicted to persist in the future, allowing more providers to benefit from setting up luxury care agencies.

Luxury care agencies offer more value to consumers when compared to conventional facilities such as hospice-based care. By this mode, the luxury care agencies will stand out against the nursing homes and provide better salaries to employees. With a correct and patient-centered approach to care, care agencies could spell the future of care in the United Kingdom. For instance, such a patient-centered approach enables the employees to acquire a higher propensity for increased responsibility. Notably, the personnel responsible for care in the luxury homes will need to do more work given the increased responsibility of satiating all clients. In this light, it is

important for the leadership to be aware of any developments in the industry in a bid to ensure that they have an enhanced sense of responsiveness to issues that would come up. Setting a luxury care facility, therefore, needs to ensure that all these considerations are put in place and that the persons or organisations setting up the facility are certain of the costs that will be involved in the setup procedures. The current situation is that everyone assumes that the services rendered in the so called luxury care homes are far much better than those in conventional and often low cost care homes. However, both operate under the same regulations and requirements. However, through its watchdog agencies, the government keeps a keen eye on the operations of all care homes with little difference in the terms of regularity of inspection of visits.

2.4 Current Attitudes Towards Luxury Care Agencies

Care homes are facilities that offer those who cannot care for themselves a place where such care can be provided at a fee. In most instances, the fee is catered by some form of insurance and the municipal councils. Under normal circumstances, care is given by relatives or care at home personnel. Increasingly, however, invalids are taken in by care homes where they are cared for by professionals. This is the care that most people associate with care homes.

There is however, a relatively new mode of care. Contrary to the traditional modes of care, customers who are not necessarily invalids may opt to enter into care centers that offer luxurious care. Research has shown that most of those who need care are no longer keen to get into care homes just for the sake of it but a good majority are opting to enter in to what is in every sense of the word, luxurious care homes. Many are increasingly appreciating the new narrative of luxury. In essence, there is a shift from the traditional and conventional focus on communication with others to a focus on the self (Sudbury-Riley et al., 2019). In line with unconventional luxury, people are now getting more focus on intangible experiences as opposed to the traditional focus on tangible entities, extended focus on consumer-oriented services as opposed to market-oriented services, and a change in the understanding of luxury where they lived experience of the customer is becoming integral to service. In this light, the perceptions and attitudes of people towards luxury are changing, making it more feasible to think in the direction of luxury care agencies.

In the past, people's attitudes towards luxury were focused on such issues as group membership, social standing, and something that was celebrated and enjoyed in a group. Currently, there is a change in perspective where luxury is something that is enjoyed for the self instead of communicating such tendencies to others. Such change of attitudes is changing the mode of consumption towards inconspicuous consumption from conspicuous consumption. People are now getting to a tendency where they do not really have to showcase to the masses that they are leading a luxurious life. The new narrative in luxury, which is more oriented to the consumer, is changing the ways in which people understand themselves.

The changing narrative in luxury leads to a changing definition of how luxury relates to the self indicates that the changes in attitudes have led to a situation where luxury is now connected to the person and can lead to self-transformation where the person leans towards becoming as opposed to possessing. Hemetsberger et al. (2019) indicate that luxury consumption is becoming eudemonic and focused on self-realization. Such a view leads to a change in the manner that the self is able to deal with its identity during the transition leading to additional focus on a person's well-being. Such a focus is also changing such spaces as care facilities and care agencies.

Consumers are also changing their perspective of care from a focus on tangible experiences as opposed to the intangible experiences of the past. People are changing their attitudes and leaning towards experiential luxury, a factor that changes attitude on luxury from such issues as taste, smell and touch and other self-directed and sensory-based modes of experiencing consumption. In the new narrative of luxury, people now conform to the diminishing importance of product-related dimensions. The changes in the new dimensions of luxury are accordingly held in the hospitality and tourism industry, where luxury has for some time been defined in terms of services offered to the consumer and the experience of the consumer in a given setting. In addition, the changing dimensions of luxury are also evident in tangible goods and the purchase of tangible goods, where people get focused on the process of purchase as opposed to the product itself.

Moreover, the perception of luxury is changing from a market perspective to a consumer perspective. This concept of luxury is all about the transition moves from the marketer's opinion to the individual's core self. In such a mode of luxury, the beneficiary of the process is the one that determines the value, and as such, the consumer defines luxury. In this mode of understanding luxury, people should change from understanding luxury as stemming and based on expensive products to one that is based on experiences that the consumers perceive. Such a perspective of luxury moves from what a marketer is able to explain and use as the indication of value to one that is based on the context of one's inner self. This approach is being applied to the care industry as well. The experiential aspect of luxury is much more important to the receiver than anything tangible.

From a traditional perspective of luxury, nice buildings, and the like including access to other facilities such the gym constitute the luxury part of care giving. This is no longer the case as

2.5 Luxury in Healthcare

In healthcare and nursing, definitions of care rotate around the interpersonal experiences between the consumers and the medical staff. In a study on 30 participants from a luxurious ophthalmic clinic, Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) state that healthcare consumers regard luxury through "moments of care." Again, Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) mention that such care moments are dependent on the carer's authentic presence, balance in power relations, and synchrony in

interpersonal relationships. In this regard, such a perspective indicates luxury with an unconventional approach where true luxury is based on the experience of humanity as evident in interpersonal relationships, as opposed to materiality in luxury.

In care perspectives and medical terminology, interpersonal relations play a significant role considering the potential complexities in healthcare exchange. Medical services and other related fields such as care agencies require that interactions between the staff and the consumers are made intimate (Kreuzer, Cado and Raies, 2020). In such a perspective, the carer's need to weigh off their negative emotions considering the health and the stakes of the consumers' health. In addition, they need to focus on the person behind a certain condition instead of laying much focus on the condition itself. When there is intimacy to the course, the negative encounters are alleviated and assist in overcoming difficulties in care. When a person experiences the positive spirit in a rather negative circumstance such as in the hands of a care facility and medical care, McColl-Kennedy et al. (2017) asserts that such an experience presents or manifests as luxury.

Unconventional luxury changes luxury from the traditional focus on materialism, indulgence, and social class to the focus on consumer's experience. This focus on the consumer's experience as one that is vested in the centrality of social interactions. In this light, luxury is experienced by subjectively experiencing humanity and the incorporation of pro-social behaviours during interpersonal exchanges. With enhanced consideration of the individual, the consistent depersonalization of care in medical facilities where patients are treated as objects of care ceases. Such attitudes are replaced by Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) and they portray that moments of care are largely based and focused on interpersonal interactions and expressions of humanity.

In medical services and related services, luxury moves from having to give. The process of giving from the caregivers leads to the definition of luxury. In this context, the staff gives the important moments of care, providing consumers with luxurious experiences that are valued by the individuals and that enhance emotional connections. Such a humanity-leaning perspective of luxury differs from the egoistic definitions of luxury that are more focused on wealth, its accumulation, and increased prestige.

In the UK healthcare sector, a startup involving a care agency is not a foreign thing since various attempts at deploying initiatives could improve both employee's and customers' satisfaction all at once. Hayter and Jackson (2020) generated this hypothesis, further concluding that customers experiences, possibly, will meaningfully affect the notion of healthcare and result in several healthcare specialists and nurses choosing careers that are not associated with predictable hospitals. Thus, the thought of the status of client welfare being irreplaceable and present might similarly be determined that a new luxury care action could prove to obtain satisfaction and gratification even though it was the client or the practitioner (Halcomb, Smyth and McInnes,

2018). Combined with the ideology that care interventions fasten the course of recovery, it may also be said that the health care sector can profit from the placement of care interventions.

However, various challenges that could scare away potential clients and employees and slow down the facility's placement could be brought about by the concept of care agency deployment. According to Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020), among the substantial purposes, healthcare experts seem to underrate care interventions as the full-time job trait of a predictable hospital and a guaranteed salary. In this sense, a care intervention might result in a problem for the management and staff, triggering team members to make decisions in a coordinated manner and make moves carefully. Nikbin et al. (2019) stated that the lack of predictability in agencies is an essential topic of discussion that should not be ignored. In the luxury setting where an emergency or a sick leave could lead to tables turning quickly, care nurses solely depend on each other. Hence, planning activities when in partnership with a caring agency would be interpreted as being ready for the unpredictable, which nurses may not view as the best choice despite the paycheck being higher than in orthodox hospitals.

In essence, care agencies are curbed with the problem of appealing to nurses and also retaining them. But, in the UK, the initiative has been made valuable due to the lack of care agencies in the country. Lapalme and Guerrero (2019) state that employees might be affected by loneliness and depression. This transient is slowly becoming a trend in the healthcare sector, thus creating nurse and patient relationships and better-quality professional skills. To rephrase that, Lapalme and Guerrero (2019) stated that not all nurses should or might be teammates, and care agencies could profit from this limitation in reshaping the idea of care provision. The compound organisation of care interventions has become outdated, allowing teammates to devise verdicts on the move. It should be recalled that not all nurses and patients are made for working with a care intervention, primarily when a luxury facility requires participation from the customer's side. In this context, it is essential to note that not all people are willing to dedicate their time and efforts to ensure that the customers receive the best possible care as required of the luxury agencies. As such, it is essential for the management to devise ways in which they are able to motivate or train their employees on the expected standards of care.

In luxury care agencies, the slightest clear idea about their potentiality is that many nurses do not view themselves as sole contractors, leading to a stereotype that either the under-skilled or underappreciated providers partner with the care agencies (Lapalme and Guerrero, 2019). Exceptional workers are needed to work in areas where high valued decisions are implemented daily. Moreover, the expenses in luxury care agencies are not made for everyone. Hence, the organisation should assess the possible advantage and disadvantages before picking areas for launching these operations. The existing prose review offers enough proof that extra care is an opportunity and a privilege that needs further research due to the need to pave the way for a

diverse health care model in the future, even though the present UK public matters may be perceived as resulting to somewhat resenting reactions.

Luxury care agencies must take into consideration the diverse aspects of interpersonal integration. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) indicate that the presence of ensuring that there is authentic presence in care relates to personalization. In this line, the author notes that the staff in the service industry should capture as many details regarding the guests as possible. Notably, the staff should aim at capturing personal details and also their desires and preferences in an attempt at creating homes out of the facilities for the guests. Additionally, Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) note that balancing power relations is an aspect that can be closely connected to experiential social hierarchy in the service industry. In the traditional realm, there are instances where luxury service has been used to exude class struggles. In this light, Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) indicates that consumers that are perceived as socio-economically inferior get to face intimidation as well as arrogance from the staff.

The third aspect of interpersonal integration comes out through interpersonal synchrony, which is different from empathy or anticipation. Empathy is the identification with another person's emotions and taking in such emotions or cognitions as the other person (Kreuzer, Cado and Raies, 2020). Contrary, empathy does not entail the performance of synchronous actions that are in tandem with the observed emotions. Against this backdrop, interpersonal synchrony closes this gap through the actions of the service personnel, or in this case, the caregivers. Essentially, the personnel understand the desires and expectations of the client and goes ahead to perform actions that are in perfect coordination with the desires and expectations of the client or in tandem with their emotions and cognitions. With such coordination of behaviors, there is joyance and rhythm in social interactions and leads to interpersonal coupling, which is well beyond empathy (Kreuzer, Cado and Raies, 2020). In essence, conformance to the diverse aspects of interpersonal integration is an issue that has been shown to lead to enhancement of care in the care agencies and the tendency towards the provision of luxury in care. The traditional notions of luxury in the service industry are used alongside improvements that make the aspect of care centered on a person and the self. Following such a progression, it is hence possible to acquire interpersonal integration, which in turn indicates an agency's adherence to the luxury care concept.

Issues that inform the aspects that consumers conceive as luxury assist in understanding luxury in care, which is offered in an experiential manner. Experiential care is based upon a set of concepts, including: lived experiences, integrated experiences, hedonic experiences, familiar experiences, personalized experiences, eudemonic experiences, and connected or disconnected experiences. All the state experiences are tied to space, place, and the community.

Before experiencing luxury care, people are marred with chaotic experiences as a result of a disconnection between service and personality or humanity, absence of informed choices, absence of advice, absence of support, and personalization of services. The crisis in care is worsened by the presence of a worrying myth that promulgates fear and anxiety (Sudbury-Riley et al., 2019). With luxury experiential care, Sudbury-Riley et al. (2019) state that services such as hospice becomes alive. Such a realization changes conversations and people stop fearing hospice and start fearing different places. The care agencies change and become homes away from the traditional homes.

In essence, the conceptualization of luxury care facilities and luxury agencies, whether they are offering care to the elderly or offering palliative care, is more connected to experiential services. When the staff change their traditional conceptualizations of service and direct their service towards experiential care, more people are likely to change their attitudes towards the care facilities and instead prefer the care agencies are homes where they can spend their time and lives in a luxurious manner. The aspect of luxury in care, despite the fact that it is an upcoming one in the United Kingdom, is one that has a lot of prospects. Given the exponential increase in the ageing population, there is an increasing need for better services that cater for the elderly and also for people with chronic illnesses. Such agencies need to diffuse from the traditional concepts of service-based care to one that adds an experiential aspect to care.

2.6 The Effect of COVID-19

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused suffering and brought fear towards older people worldwide. On April 26, 2020, the fatality rate of individuals aged 80 years and above was five times the global average: the virus had taken the lives of 193,710 people. As the virus continued to spread, the mortality rate of older people continued to go up even higher (United Nations, 2020). The pandemic brought about other effects such as increased unemployment and poverty, health care denial for COVID-19 related and unrelated conditions, the trauma of discrimination and stigma, and the impact on individuals' mental health and wellbeing. The efforts to protect older people should not be overlooked due to their various roles, such as caregivers and incredible positivity and resilience. We need to view the diversity of older individuals. For example, women are often over-represented among older people and care workers who look after them. There is a need for international organisations, businesses, communities, companies to recognize the impact older people have on the COVID-19, such as caregivers and health care workers. Hence, we are required to do everything possible to preserve the dignity and rights of old individuals at all times.

Across the globe, the COVID-19 pandemic posed various risks among the older generation, such as the risk between life and death. Although all age groups are prone to contracting the disease, older individuals over 80 years are significantly at a higher risk of severe disease infection

(United Nations, 2020). They are dying five times than the standard rate. People above 70 have more than one underlying condition placing them at a higher risk of the severe impact of the disease. In terms of medical care and therapies, older individuals may face discrimination during decision-making. Globally, older people fail to provide essential healthcare services, especially in developing countries. Further, the pandemic also caused the lagging behind of other healthcare services, increasing the risks to older people.

Based on the impacts stated, the following are various priorities for action. There is a need to reinforce solidarity and social inclusion during social distancing. The restrictions imposed on movement can disrupt care and support for older people (United Nations, 2020). Social distancing is essential but requires to be accompanied with targeted care and social support for older people, such as increasing their access to modern technology. There is also a need to ensure that decisions concerning the old people are made following the commitment to the right to health and dignity. Every person has the right to access proper health, and every life has equivalent value. Certain risks need to be fully addressed and adequately monitored, such as neglect, age discrimination, violence and mistreatment in care institutions.

Further, there is a need to enhance older people's participation, educate them, and share good practices. There is a need to consult and expand partnerships with older adults and ensure that they are fully included in policies that affect them (United Nations, 2020). In addition, we need to cut down the stigma against older adults. The virus has highlighted that older people are invisible in public data analysis. Hence, effective public policies should include innovative approaches, evidence and data differentiated by age and sex, and appropriate economic and social characteristics. Additionally, there is a need to integrate the older people in social, economic and humanitarian response to the virus. The impact of the virus on social and economic factors on older adults requires to be addressed both in the recovery and crisis phase. Hence, there is a need to participate in social protection and strengthen national and global legal outlines to protect the rights of older individuals. COVID-19 has caused and continues to cause adverse effects across the globe. As a result, it is essential to ensure proper planning in caring institutions and communities that provide a home for the aged and the dignity and human rights of the old individuals.

The pandemic has impacted the old individuals' rights, health, and long-term care services. The pandemic has caused both direct and indirect challenges towards the ancient people, such as access to healthcare. In such a threatening pandemic, older people face several challenges when accessing healthcare and treatment. For instance, many people, especially the poorest, have little or no access to care in developing countries, further contributing to poor healthcare systems. Other measures, such as the concentration of resources to the pandemic and lockdowns have created a barrier for the older adults with other underlying conditions to obtain health care services, increasing their vulnerability to the disease. Other challenges affecting older adults

include neglect, abuse, and violence. Additionally, older adults living in emergency settings such as refugee camps face overcrowding issues that increase the risk of contracting the virus and limited access to clean sanitation and water, health care increasing their vulnerability.

To curb the challenges affecting older adults, the following are various recommendations to put in place; there is a need to reinforce services to protect and prevent old individuals, especially women, from abuse and violence such as neglect and domestic violence. Authorities need to ensure that the plans and strategies affect the old migrants and refugees' access to proper healthcare and treatment. There is a need to ensure that older people with other underlying conditions and those living alone are identified and attended to early. Medical decisions based on individual clinical examinations need to be put on the best accessible scientific evidence. Further, governments need to ensure that care services such as mental health services are available for workers and workers at home-based care and institutional settings. Visitor policies in hospitals and residential places need to balance the need for connection and family and the protection of others.

While measures such as social distancing and movement restrictions are essential in curbing the spread of the virus, such efforts lead to isolation worsening the health outcomes of older people. Many old individuals, especially those living alone, rely on community support and services, and these measures limit the provision of these services. Hence, authorities should increase such efforts to reach out to many older people and expand the necessary support services (United Nations, 2020). Movement restrictions have also impacted the well-being and mental health of older people. The conditions prevented visitors from visiting family members in the care homes, which can negatively affect highly care-dependent and those with a cognitive decline. To prevent such impacts, legal and social services need to be maintained despite the social distancing measures.

Further, care facilities should be strengthened to respect the older people's autonomy and rights. Terms that do not stereotype and stigmatize older adults should be highly used. Hence, we should avoid labeling them as vulnerable because this creates a feeling of bias. Older adults need to have access to information on the various measures to protect themselves from the virus. This can be achieved when the authorities work with multiple volunteers and community organisations using the different available formats accessible to many people. Mobile services can also be increased to reach out to those in isolated places. Also, older people can be supported with modern devices to act as an alternative way of communicating with relatives when physical movement has been restricted.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

The research focuses on understanding how the implementation of luxury healthcare affects individuals and healthcare organisations. This conceptual framework focuses on essential concepts that include the existence of luxury care homes, attitudes towards care luxury homes, advantages and disadvantages of luxury health care, the effectiveness of rendering services and luxurious experiences in care. Specifically, this conceptual framework is grounded on assumptions from Veblen's Theory of the Leisure Class, which holds that the purpose of luxury consumption is to display wealth and social status (Knott-Fayle, 2019). The study explores the current development of leisure home care using Veblen's theory of instincts and status emulation to highlight the link with social and economic capitalism. To achieve this, the research will rely on theoretical assessment alongside interpretive analysis of existing literature and qualitative analysis of the contemporary leisure care sector. An integral aspect of Veblen's theory pertains to assessing the pecuniary standards of living.

Moreover, the theory states that once an individual develops a certain scale of decent consumption and becomes an element of one's scheme of life, it becomes extremely difficult to scale down because it directly affects physical comfort and becomes necessary, especially when it involves life or health. Leisure care homes affect patients' experience, comfort, attitudes, and perception in long-term care (Knott-Fayle, 2019). Traditional long-term facilities are underfunded, understaffed, and lack the necessary resources required to deliver the highest level of care commensurate with the living standards enjoyed by patients before their admission. The existence of luxury care homes is based on individualized and personal care, which allows members of the care team to respond to requests promptly. The perceived comfort by patients in long-term facilities facilitates recovery and enhanced health outcomes because it affects their psychological wellbeing. Kreuzer, Cado and Raïes (2020) reveal that patients' attitudes about the physical environment and the facility design improve the delivery of care and promote safety concerns.

Therefore, Veblen's theory demonstrates that leisure home care represents a necessity in enhancing the quality of life, improving care delivery, and patient-centered care. Leisure consumption is a prerequisite for human dignity, especially involving desirable products. The theory suggests that the convention scheme of consumption does not easily change. For that reason, the current shift to leisure home care does not only result in superior care but prestige and comfort of the patient (Liljas, Brattström, Burström, Schön and Agerholm, 2019). The situation manifests in luxury health care that describes health as a "luxury" rather than a necessity since stakeholders believe that human contact is becoming a luxury good. As a result, stakeholders are considering increasing the luxury of personal care and human interaction. Therefore, Veblen's Theory of the Leisure Class is crucial for this study as it permits us to determine the extent to which patients and staff are willing to go to achieve an enhanced quality of life.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Chapter Overview

A significant effort is made to clarify and provide distinctions between research methodology and research method. The chapter, thus, includes an explanation and justification of the research philosophy and the research approach. There is also an explanation and justification of the data collection and data analysis procedures. Additionally, the chapter examines, explains and justifies the research instruments including the reliability and validity and a statement indicating conformance to proper research ethics.

3.2 Research Philosophy and Justification

Notably, the research process employs an interpretivism philosophy. According to Scauso (2020), interpretivism enables the exploration of novel strategies that luxury facilities in the UK use to support the elderly in care. Scauso (2020) stresses that interpretivism offers a novel way to make inquiries in support or disapproval of new themes and ideas. In essence, the author will look into the strategies that the facilities currently use in the provision of care and the possibility and feasibility of enhancing the “luxuriousness” of future facilities for provision of care for the aged members of the population.

Additionally, the research will employ an inductive approach. An inductive approach, as Scauso (2020) notes, allows the data to reproduce new meanings through the identification of various patterns as well as relationships between the variables under study. Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018) highlights that this type of research searches for patterns from observations, develops explanations for these observed patterns and develops hypothesis leading to theories about a phenomenon. According to Woiceshyn and Daellenbach (2018), hypothesis and theories cannot be formed at the beginning because the researcher will apply inductive analysis only after making extensive observations of the phenomena in question. Observations may be in terms of reviewing available literature on a subject or physically observing a phenomenon in its natural settings. In inductive research method, the researcher is at liberty to alter the direction of the study even after it has commenced and progressed awhile. This is because the patterns being unravelled as the inquiry progresses determine the direction and depth of inquiry needed to answer the research questions(s).

The objective of inductive research is to generate patterns and relationships and give meaning to such patterns and relations, which can be utilized to build a theory or an explanation (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach 2018). This approach aims to generate meanings from the data set collected in order to identify patterns and relationships to build a theory and make conclusions.

Inductive reasoning begins with detailed observations of the world, which moves towards more abstract generalisations and ideas. When following an inductive approach, the researcher will begin with a topic and progress towards developing empirical generalisations by identifying preliminary relationships as the research progresses. As explained by Azungah (2018), research hypothesis are only formed after concluding the observations. At this stage, the researcher is sure about the type and nature of the findings.

In summary, inductive inquiry moves from data and progresses to theory. In other words, researchers will move from the specific (information collected through observations and literature review) to the general (theory or explanation about the phenomena)

3.3 Research Approach and Justification

The researcher will review credible sources mainly, peer-reviewed journals. Literature review will be conducted from the various databases using distinct keywords and key phrases. Such keywords and phrases will include luxury in care, luxury in care homes, the effectiveness of luxury care, attitudes towards luxury, attitudes towards luxury care, and feasibility of luxury care, amongst others that proved relevant. The researcher will also apply combinations of the keywords and phrases using Boolean operators, including “AND” and “OR” words.

This review will provide a wealth of current data and other relevant information that the researcher will use in formulating the research hypothesis, conceptual framework and the research methodology. Again, the researcher will be allowed to narrow down on areas that are not adequately covered with a view to closing the gaps in knowledge about luxury care in the United Kingdom.

3.4 Research Method and Justification

The research methodology is qualitative in nature. The reason for choosing qualitative research method for this study is because it helps in gaining an understanding of underlying opinions. In that case, this research method aids in uncovering trends in thoughts and dive deeper into the issue of concern. Besides, Squires and Dorsen (2018) assert that qualitative research is essential in studying issues that entail regulations across all professions, including health and nursing. In essence, qualitative research is essential in espousing stakeholders' perspectives and ensuring that the views of relevant stakeholders are captured when implementing policy change (Squires and Dorsen, 2018). In this research, a qualitative method is feasible since it will reveal human perceptions, opinions, actions and even experiences. According to McNab (2020), a qualitative strategy will enable a proper understanding of diverse human experiences in care.

3.5 Data Collection Method and Justification

Due to COVID-19 safety guidelines, the best way to gather information will be through reviewing the printed sources. The review of the details of the sources provides the basis of making the appropriate inquiries in order to understand the dynamics underpinning the care industry. Literature review enables one to analyse, assess, synthesize, and comment on study findings on a given research topic in order to avoid replicating already published works and to identify gaps that the research could fill, thus creating a new understanding of a phenomena.

This study will employ a review of available literature with the aim of assessing, analysing, and synthesising the literature on the research topic in a way that allows theoretical frameworks and methods to emerge. In this regard, publications for review will include peer-reviewed journals that offers in-depth insights about the topic.

The data will be collected from existing credible sources. The process involves the identification, recording, making meanings, understanding, and eventually transmitting the information. Notably, the literature review is the actual data collection method where the researcher focuses on and uses a comprehensive methodology to organise the data. In essence, this data collection technique is a justifiable since the process of conducting the review is akin to the research itself, whereas the reviewed information makes up the data in the research. As such, review of the literature can stand alone as a whole research process.

In turn, secondary sources, mainly peer-reviewed journal articles, are the ones used in this study. Importantly, the sources used were reliable since they provided a thorough, well-reasoned theory and discussion based on strong evidence. Simultaneously, these sources were written by experts in the discipline and they are free of errors and bias. With this in mind, these sources are current and reliable, implying that the written by trustworthy authors and organisations. As a result, these sources are dependable and readers can verify that the information included is accurate and up-to-date.

Besides, data to be collected will be qualitative in nature and it should consist of descriptions of services rendered in both conventional and luxury care homes, descriptions of the advantages and disadvantages likely to face a stay in luxury care homes, descriptions and discussions about how people feel about luxury care homes, and any other relevant information. As much as it would be appropriate and important to get information from residents and staff of luxury care homes, due to the prevailing COVID-19 pandemic, this source of data will be unavailable.

3.6 Data Analysis Methods

To search for relevant themes across the sources used, theme analysis will be conducted. Specifically, thematic analysis is the method of choice for identifying, analysing, and reporting themes within qualitative data. A thematic analysis proves a feasible methodology since the researcher could use it to identify prevalent themes and patterns in the research that could lead to insights that answers the research questions. Kiger and Varpio (2020) highlights that thematic analysis requires that the researcher reads a data set and identifies patterns or themes that resonate across the data. In the current study, the researcher read across various pieces of literature on care, identified patterns relationships and themes that answered the research question.

Again, thematic analysis proved to be a good method for analysing qualitative data generated in the literature review as it provided the researcher with an opportunity and the ability to generate new insights about the data collected through literature review. The researcher will be able to analyse, present and express such insights with reference to the same data.

The first step of analysing data involved initial reading and precoding to familiarize the researcher with the many data sets on care homes (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). The process of data familiarisation involves reading through the different pieces of information and coming up with insights, concepts, and themes that were likely to answer the research question. As a result, the researcher will get a sense of all data material so as to understand the overall meaning of the sources' statements. The second step involves the researcher going through the selected works in order to look for patterns and relationships as well as new insights common with the various sets of reviewed data (Snyder, 2019). The researcher will look for meanings across the reviewed literature and creating codes that represent the diverse insights. Consequently, preliminary categories and themes will be successively identified based on the initial coding. Using these codes developed during the literature review, the researcher then went through the dataset to come up with excerpts from the literature that represent the data set (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). The researcher will ensure that the codes to be developed have diverse excerpts from different sources. The last step in this process will involve defining and naming the themes and reporting the analysis.

Also, the researcher will ensure that all the identified themes had enough supporting data. Those lacking in this crucial aspect, which is lacking enough empirical support from reviewed literature, will be discarded and will not analysed. The last set of themes developed from this process will be used to write the narrative that forms the discussion and the results of the study.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

Research ethics involve requirements on daily work, the protection of dignity of subjects and the publication of the information in the research. Ethics refers to a system of principles, which can critically change previous considerations about choices and actions. Ethics in this research will deal with how the researcher will make concerning what is right and wrong when collecting data, analysing the data and ultimately when making conclusions arrived at. The major ethical considerations in this research will include beneficence and role conflict.

Beneficence:

As a qualitative research, it is difficult to predict the outcomes of this research. As such, the researcher will strive to ensure that whatever comes out will not be of harm to anybody but will be of benefit. If the research findings will prove that, the whole exercise will be in futility and therefore not beneficial, it will raise ethical questions on why the researcher will waste time and resources in the first place. By formulating a good proposal, the researcher will avoid arriving at useless and possibly harmful conclusions.

Role Conflict:

The researcher will have no prior business with any home care institution in the country but will only be interested in generating new insights in the business of luxury care homes. Thus, the researcher will explore the question of whether the care touted as luxury care is truly luxurious in the eyes of the recipients, the general public and the staff involved in the luxury care homes. Therefore, the ethical issue of conflict of interest will be avoided.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND RESULTS

4.1 Sample Description and Sources Used

The study reviewed resources from the credible journals on home care. The resources used as summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Sources of Data

Authors	Topic	Source	Findings	Codes Identified In The Sources	Themes Resulting From The Codes
Gordon, A. L., Goodman, C., Davies, S. L., Deming, T., Gage, H., Meyer, J., and Zubair, M., 2018.	Optimal healthcare delivery to care homes in the UK	<i>Age and Ageing</i> , 47(4), 595-603	<p>Collaboration among care home staff is integral to optimal healthcare provision in care homes.</p> <p>Nurses and caregivers expertise is essential but other services can be structured to offer extra support that enables nurses and caregivers to focus on fundamental medical work.</p>	<p>Specialist care for older individuals living with dementia.</p> <p>Investment in care home-specific work</p>	Luxury in care
Sudbury-Riley, L., Hunter-Jones, P., Al-Abdin, A., Lewin, D. and Spence, R. 2019.	Conceptualizing experiential luxury in palliative care:	<i>Journal of Business Research</i> , 116, pp.446-457.	For hospice consumers the needs instead of choice take precedence, such as a need to manage illness and a need to return agency.	<p>Understanding conventional luxury</p> <p>Understanding luxury through lived experiences</p>	Luxury in care

			Luxury in care can help to extend a patient' lifespan, service provision and thus patient experience.		
Smith, D., 2018.	Care homes for the elderly: Where are we now?	https://www.grantthornton.co.uk/globalassets/1.-member-firms/united-kingdom/pdf/documents/care-homes-for-the-elderly-where-are-we-now.pdf	Care home operators are starting to offer the level of support and rehabilitation that is necessary. There have been several investments by private equity in developing and building out new high-end, purpose-built homes.	A substantial increase in the demand for elderly care beds over the coming decade and beyond. UK needs at least 75,000 extra elderly care beds by 2030.	Increasing bed space in care homes
Liljas, A., Brattström, F., Burström, B., Schön, P. and Agerholm, J., 2019	Impact of integrated care on patient-related outcomes among older people	<i>International Journal of Integrated Care</i> , 19(3), pp.1-16.	Integrated care may hospital admission rates and lengths of hospital stay.	Increase in elderly population	Luxury in care
Kreuzer, M., Cado, V. and Raies, K., 2020	Moments of care: How interpersonal interactions contribute to luxury experiences	<i>Journal of Business Research</i> , 116, pp.482-490.	In luxury health care, individuals experience high-class offerings such as hotel-like amenities, luxurious interior	Healthcare consumers experience moments of care through authentic presence,	Luxury in care

	of healthcare consumers.		designs, and advanced technology. Components that are experienced in luxury care homes include interpersonal effort, interpersonal engagement, problem resolution, interpersonal distance and time commitment.	balanced power relationship, and interpersonal synchrony.	
Emmer De Albuquerque Green, C., Tinker, A. and Manthorpe, J., 2021.	Human rights and care homes for older people:	<i>The International Journal of Human Rights</i> , pp.1-23.	The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in the creation of luxury care homes to protect residents from infection. The pandemic has increased the governments' continued important role in human rights protection.	The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in the creation of luxury care homes to protect residents from infection	COVID-19

The sources above comprises of codes, which when combined results in themes. Firstly, Gordon et al. (2018) reveals codes that include specialist care for older individuals living with dementia and the need to invest in care home-specific work. These codes by Gordon et al. (2018) leads to the formation of luxury care theme. Secondly, Sudbury-Riley et al. (2019) highlights two codes that include understanding conventional luxury and understanding luxury through lived experiences. These codes by Sudbury-Riley et al. (2019) leads to the formation of luxury in care as a theme. Thirdly, Smith (2018) stresses codes that include a substantial increase in the demand for elderly care beds over the coming decade and beyond and UK needs at least 75,000 extra

elderly care beds by 2030. These codes by Smith (2018) results in the creation of increasing bed space in care homes theme. Fourthly, Liljas et al. (2019) reports the code, which is the increase in elderly population in care homes that calls for the need for integrated care. This code by Liljas et al. (2019) leads to the theme of luxury in care. Fifthly, Kreuzer, Cado, and Raies (2020) shares the code, patients experience moments of care through authentic presence, balanced power relationship, and interpersonal synchrony. This code results matches the theme of luxury in care. Lastly, Green et al. (2021) share some codes that include the COVID-19 epidemic leading to development of luxury care homes and the pandemic increasing the government role in improving the health of elderly theory the creation of luxury care homes. These two codes leads to the development of COVID-19 as a theme. Hence, the sources contain three main themes that include luxury in care, increasing bed space in care homes, and COVID-19.

4.2: Specific Methods: Theme Analysis

Literature review has come up with several crosscutting issues, which all support the establishment of more care homes. Reviewed sources does support the development of more care homes. It goes further and explains not just the reasons for increasing the numbers but also gives irrefutable facts that support establishment of luxury homes too. The economic potential for luxury care homes is also evidenced by a host of literature.

Issue 1: Increasing Bed Space in Care Homes

An in-depth analysis of available literature shows that the emergence and consequent spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has had a very pronounced and negative effect on small care homes. The effect is more pronounced on those care homes that were already vulnerable, those that do not have the scale to cope with the loss of occupancy because of COVID-19 and those that do not have the right infrastructure to protect against the virus in a better way.

The most visible effect of the COVID-19 is the acceleration of the rate at which care homes are closing. Literature review also shows that the resulting closure of many care homes creates the need to open new care homes which are able to protect themselves better from the vagaries wrought out by the changing business environment in the social, legal and economic environments (Hsu, 2020). Literature shows that only those care homes with the resilience to stand up to external threats will survive. Literature reviewed also show the need to for more care homes and the need to upscale the market (Brame 2020). As such, the need to create new homes for the elderly is apparent, giving room for the creation of more luxury care homes.

Above the COVID-19 pandemic, other major and minor reasons, supporting the creation of care homes is emerging. One of the reasons, according to the reviewed literature, which could promote the creation of new care homes, can be glimpsed from the rising population of people who may need others to take of them. Marina (2021) holds that care homes are better placed than relatives and or neighbours to undertake this service.

The UK and other developed countries are experiencing a rapid rise in their aged populations meaning that the number of people who will need care home services is rising. These are individuals over the age of 85 years. Looking at the UK's population pyramid over the various census periods since the 70's show an increase in the proportion of the aged in the population. Various demographers predict that by the year 2050, the population of people aged over 85 years will be rising at an annual rate exceeding the population growth rate (Nash, A. 2019.). This increase in the population of people, most likely to need care home services call for the establishments of more such facilities.

More evidence of the need for increasing the number of care homes is the rising prevalence of lifestyle diseases among the aged. Records of people suffering from debilitating conditions such as dementia, arthritis, Alzheimer's and early onset of senility show a steady rise over the years. The rate at which such people are being diagnosed with such conditions has recently seen a rapid rise in the UK and other western countries and Japan (Cristea et al., 2020). Such conditions immobilize sufferers with the result that they are unable to take care of themselves. Such people will definitely require the services offered by care homes.

The increasing occurrence of these diseases and conditions is not confined to people in the aged category (Hung, 2018). The population of younger people, including people in their 40s diagnosed with conditions requiring home care is also rising. Such people will also require the services offered by care homes.

Literature available shows that there is an increasing growth in the population needing care from all demographic categories of the population. However, this is against a falling number of bed space in care homes per 100 people (Ettelt et al., 2020). Literature reviewed clearly indicates an urgent need to increase care home beds to cope with the rising demand. However, it is proving to be impractical for existing homes to expand their bed capacity given the challenges in funding amid dwindling customers and more restrictive rules and regulations. All this requires massive commitment in capital, which older care homes will not afford hence the need for other investors with the financial muscle to step in.

Brame (2020) indicates that the existing care homes are becoming obsolete. In this case, more homes are becoming outdated with the standards of care improving and specifications on care changing more than it has been in the past. There is an increase in the need to build homes that are fit-for-purpose and inclusive of additional facilities like wet rooms, wider corridors, ample leisure activities, living facilities, and full en-suite units. In this light, Brame (2020) indicates that most homes are struggling to meet new expectations and may just find themselves having to close down as customers decamp to better-equipped and organised facilities.

There is an additional need to create new homes as a result of the ones closing due to failure to meet standards. Because of the pandemic, most care homes are facing financial stress as a result of the increase in staff costs and challenges in funding (Gordon et al., 2018). With the increasing rate of closures, it is essential that there is additional creation of new homes, which gives room for luxury care homes.

The luxury care home market is experiencing a boom owing to the changing standards and an influx of a new private-paying market (Barker et al., 2021). With such a market, there is pressure for operators to deliver high standard care. Brame (2020) reports that there is an increasing adaptation of new designs where care homes are coming in with memory integration, taking into consideration people suffering from dementia and Alzheimer's. With the additional problem of COVID-19, it is necessary that more comfortable and spacious homes are built that ensure social distancing, limited touch points, and safer areas for visitors that also have enhanced communication.

The upcoming generation of people over 85 years is composed of more affluent and high-income members. Brame (2021) thinks that Most of these members cannot qualify for state-funded residential care and are willing to pay a premium for the best possible care. The market, which is self-funded, is driving the new developments in care facilities across the United Kingdom. In essence, there are more private homes growing, and that is expected to perform strongly against the current cases, driving the urge to have more success in luxury care facilities. Assertion by Brame (2021) gains significance from the observation that more people are dying from dementia than heart-related conditions.

Improvement of care for the elderly has a positive impact on their health and longevity. Emmer De Albuquerque Green, Tinker and Manthorpe (2021) narrate that the life expectancy in the UK is up to 89 and 85 years for women and men, respectively. While the area is amongst the most affluent in the country, there are more cases of dementia, yet it has the lowest dementia beds per resident. In this light, the author indicates that there is a high cost of maintaining the elderly to such levels, an issue that is directly related to a high cost of care. In essence, the elderly need some stimulation and activities that will enable them to cope with life in a better way. Essentially, lack of such activities leads to an increase in depression, adding a toll on the patients and their families. Care homes need to ensure the provision of more stimulating activities to reduce cases of depression.

Issue 2: Luxury in Care

Luxury is now getting connected to a consumer's lived experiences. In this mode of luxury, it can be noted that luxury stems from people's daily experiences. The lived experiences are based on such concepts as time and space, community, individuality, wellbeing, and other life dimensions that are considered meaningful by the consumer. From the lived experiences perspective, the consumer's perceptions of luxury change. Moreover, the new perspective of

luxury, the traditional modes of luxury still exist and matter, but the consumer is the one that defines whether it is luxury considering the experience. Previously, the marketer led the definition of luxury, but currently, the customer's lived experience defines luxury.

Issue 3: COVID-19

The pandemic has revealed gaps in the accessibility of specific age data. Data is crucial in identifying the full impact of COVID-19 and establishing proper forms of response. Further, the perspectives, voices, and expertise are often not utilized in areas where older and vulnerable individuals are affected by the decisions (United Nations, 2020). Hence, it is essential to broaden partnerships with civil society and others to harness the knowledge of the older adults, listen to their voices and ensure that they have free, meaningful and active participation. Appropriate platforms need to establish better practices and ways to develop solutions that seek to protect the rights of older individuals in times of crisis and beyond. To achieve this, there is a need to review rules for data on social welfare and ensure that the older people are included in crucial data. In addition, there is a need to provide clear standards for reporting cases concerning COVID-19 to capture risk factors among older individuals such as age, sex, and other underlying health conditions.

The pandemic has brought several challenges to humanity and has posed various threats to lives, health, wellbeing, and older people's rights. It is essential to minimize such risks by addressing older individuals' human rights and needs in fighting the pandemic. However, some of the risks are not new. Older individuals have been subjected to inadequate protection and often overlooked in specific programs and national policies. The pandemic acts as a chance to stage an equitable, more inclusive and age-friendly society guided by the agenda of Sustainable Development to *Leave No One Behind*.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION ON THE FINDINGS AND THE RESULTS

5.1 Outcome Of Literature Review On Care Homes

The advent of luxury homes is an idea that is slowly catching up with more people accepting its inevitability. According to (2020), luxury homes are now the trend as more people needing the care provided are willing to pay for the same. The number of people opting to go into what can be considered luxury care homes is increasing with the decrease in number of the traditional care homes for various reasons. The stricter regulations imposed by the regulatory authorities is helping to boost the rise in the numbers as the same regulations constrict the traditional care homes. The standards, as they currently stand impose very high standards in terms of the specifications in the physical aspects as well as in the care itself. This finding is in contradiction with what was expected.

According to initial reviews, most residents in care homes have the local authority paying for their internment here. Additionally, most of the residents have some form of insurance that pay some of the services. However, with the majority of local governments severely lacking in funding, the amount they can afford these days is very much below what the regulations require. This gap has been filled by the luxury care homes.

5.2 Results and Literature Review

Some issues that became apparent in the literature review are the increase in the feasibility and potential for more advanced care facilities and care homes for the elderly. There is a rising segment of care personnel that are providing a rather nontraditional model of care that is founded on luxury or high-end care. Nemzer and Neymotin (2020) reveal that there has been a problem in conceptualizing this model of care, especially amongst legal, medical, and ethical factions. The concepts of this model of care are based on quality and personalized care, enhanced access to service, and continuity of individualized care.

While traditional insurance plans do not pay for some services, there are patients who are willing to pay a lot of money to access these extra services from their own resources as well as insurance covers that could cover most of the needs if not all. In light of the challenges that the COVID-19 pandemic has brought about in the world today, more people are opting to invest more in healthcare, making the option of luxury care homes a feasible business opportunity.

There is an increasing appeal to physical perfection in society today. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) stress that there is an ever-expanding focus on such features as cosmetic surgeries, picture-perfect representations of the self and raising self-esteem in people that focuses on perfectionism. There is a high rise in the demand for plastic surgery in the UK, as a report by the British Association of Aesthetic Plastic Surgeons (BAAPS) reveals that its doctors are reporting

a 70 per cent increase in requests for plastic surgeries and cosmetic procedures (Meeson, 2020). Luxury brands need to do more work on upping their retail service experience as consumers are now choosing more luxury encounters. Accordingly, Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) indicates that the healthcare industry is becoming a significant area for luxury service marketing. In this light, it is essential to consider luxury in care homes as part of luxury in healthcare services.

In service marketing, healthcare is an emotive issue that leads to an intense debate. Blut et al. (2019) state that in most cases, the intense emotions arise from lack of familiarity with the service or lack of knowledge on the service outcomes. In this regard, when conducting research on luxury marketing, it is essential that stakeholders and researchers are careful on how to handle the emotional issue. In order to ensure that the issue is carefully dealt with in research, it is important to ensure that researchers take heed of the customer experience initiatives.

5.3 Contributions

While several challenges exist in delivering luxurious healthcare services, this field has a lot of business potential. Although such challenges exist in almost all industries, the healthcare industry is mostly affected by these challenges. Kreuzer, Cado and Raies (2020) mention that luxury care is vested on connections that exist between hospitality and luxurious patient experience. According to Peltier et al. (2013), there is a necessary bond between patients and caregivers, and that is not common in other services. Notably, in care services, the patient should not be viewed as a customer considering that service at this time entails offering services to a vulnerable population.

There are diverse environments and contexts of care, making the providers responsible for the creation of positive experiences for their patients (Kreuzer, Cado and Raies, 2020). The using and leveraging insights garnered from healthcare research, healthcare providers could manage to handle patient expectations and consequently improve patient-provider relations. With the transformations in the healthcare industry, so are customer expectations and patient experience.

Care homes largely operate to provide an essential service to care of those who are unable to take care of themselves because of their age and or medical condition. The basis for providing care is more on benevolence and compassion than the need to make money though residents are required to pay (Hsu, 2020). However, from the trend seen in the literature revived, care homes are now being operated like businesses with profits in mind. However, the residents are demanding better services especially where they are able to fund their stay themselves and providers are ready to provide any service on demand as long as the client can pay for the service. Again, regulators are imposing stricter regulations that guard against exploitation. Regulations ensure that the services rendered are of the best quality, and are provided in a safe and clean environment by qualified personnel.

There is increasing demand for qualification of caregivers and other staff working with elderly patients. Currently, staff found in these facilities is often highly trained and highly motivated. Apart from meeting the basic standards as per the regulations, the level of care provided is now largely based on the ability of the customer to pay. This has opened the way for luxury home care with facilities providing the physical luxury in terms of facilities and range of services provided as well as in care luxury by providing personalized care services.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Chapter Overview

This chapter discusses the conclusions arrived at, the research Implications and the recommendations. Again, the chapter looks at the unique contributions it has made in understanding the dynamics of the care home industry.

6.2 Conclusion (Recap Research Objectives and Results)

Care homes are an integral part of the United Kingdom's service sector. The first objective involved understanding the effectiveness of the luxury long-term care in UK. From the review, it is apparent that the sector has no prescribed model of operation but offers a rich and varied mix of businesses, from large corporate operators providing in excess of 10,000 beds to sole traders with one or two homes. To date, luxury care homes are increasingly becoming apparent and are now a part of the mix with clients able and willing to pay for luxury care. The sector is now dominated by independent operators. They provide better services compared together services such as hospice-based care. Luxury has merged as a part and parcel of care because it is a critical element of lived experiences. For that reason, the quality of care should be defined from the perspective of recipients of care instead of the market led mode of delivery. For that reason, premium services enables elders to access personal based care considering individuality, space and time, and community.

Moreover, the study focused on understanding the perception of the different actors of luxury long-term care. The emergency of a wealthy club of elderly people, proliferation of information and awareness of the luxury services, and increase in the number of chronic disease necessitate the need for premium service to enhance the quality of life and lived experiences. There is a paradigm shift from the traditional market oriented services to a consumer oriented model, which emphasise on personalized care. However, it has drawn criticism from some stakeholders especially those who argue that luxury and premium service focus on profit while neglecting essential matters such as benevolence, humanity, and lived experiences.

The study demonstrate that luxury care homes are effective when it comes to offering high-quality care to UK elderly residents. The reason why they are effective is because of the specialized services offered by trained caregivers and nurses. For that reason, UK residents are supposed to be informed about the benefits linked with taking patients, mainly elderly population to luxury care homes. As well, consumers, the public and staff in luxury care homes have positive attitude towards luxury care agencies since they feel that patients are the ones benefiting more from the improved services. For that reason, there is a likelihood for success when it comes to the implementation of luxury care homes in UK.

Ultimately, COVID-19 pandemic has brought about in the world today, more people are opting to invest more in healthcare, making the option of luxury care homes a feasible business opportunity. The COVID-19 situation has made UK government to intervene to minimize threats to lives, health and older people's rights by addressing older individuals' human rights and needs in fighting the pandemic.

6.3 Research Implications/Recommendations/Contributions (Theoretical and Practical)

Life in care homes is viewed by many as dreary, negatively focussed and devoid of meaningful experiences. However, luxury care homes have changed that perception with many people opting to have the care homes as home from home. Services offered and the ways they are offered have the potential to add meaning to life. Luxury homes now present a meaningful, fun filled and comfortable living to those who can afford an extravagance not seen before. The market for luxury care homes is expanding rapidly with more people entering the retirement age. Coupled with the increase in lifestyle diseases and conditions that require one to be cared for, the market is set to expand. However, the costs are rising as well as standards rise and regulations being more pronounced.

6.4 Research Limitations and Further Research

Research into luxury care homes is ongoing and not as advanced as in other areas. This is mainly because the area is relatively new. Much of the data reviewed is not strictly on luxury care homes but in care homes and the care industry in general. This presented limitation to the researcher in terms of searching for relevant materials from published works. Again the fact that the COVID-19 pandemic constrained the researcher in that it was not possible to interview players in the field at least to shed more light in the findings or make clarifications. However, the researcher has tried to connect with experts in the area whose opinions have shaped the study.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Supervision Meeting and Contact Log Book

The logbook is to record your progress through the Masters Dissertation. It is evidence that you have met various criteria associated with the dissertation.

1. Explained meetings, use of MS Teams Channel, LD7050 site. Importance of uploading documents in advance of meetings, and importance of attending workshops.
 2. Comments on Topic/Proposal
 - a. Interesting topic, but need to focus – will you look at the market for Luxury Care from the consumer perspective or the business perspective?
 - b. Objectives need to be focused as well – and relate to luxury in all instances.
 - c. Justification for focus on UK needs more discussion.
 3. Revise Introduction, draft Literature Review accordingly. (and change “truce”??)
 4. Tashfia to contact me when ready to discuss next draft.
-
1. Mid-term review done. Progress is adequate, but data collection/methodology causes concerns as it is not well-understood.
 2. Objective 2 – why look at investment?
 3. Literature review should end with Conceptual Framework.
 4. Methodology should discuss what you WILL do, not what was done. Remember – you cannot conduct focus groups without Ethical approval.
 5. Data Analysis discussion is confusing, you are doing Thematic Analysis or Grounded Theory?
 6. Continue with draft, contact when ready to discuss next draft and Ethics form.
-
7. Documents uploaded to the wrong location, not much time for me to find and review.
 8. Not sure I understand Objective 1 vs 2?
 9. Conceptual framework needs much more explanation/discussion, and a diagram would help!
 10. Research Philosophy should be discussed first, before method/approach. And this section should describe what you WILL do, not what you’ve done.
 11. Data collection is unclear – surely you’re going to review data outside of what was discussed in Section 2??? (don’t call your data collection a “Literature Review”) You need to specify exactly where you will collect your data, criteria for collection, justification, etc. etc.
 12. Ethics discussion needs to be more specific to the research.
 13. Section 4.1 – what are “reputable” sources?
 14. Conclusion needs to recap each objective.

1. You need to include more on how the thematic analysis was done – table of coding etc.
 2. Headings in Section 5 are guidelines for discussion, not section headings. What are the themes that were identified and how do they relate to your Conceptual Framework from Section 2?
 3. Reviewed comments from previous meeting, to ensure they are understood.
 4. Still unsure about objectives 1 vs 2? And how they impact the Conceptual Framework? Conceptual Framework needs to result from Literature Review.
 5. Research Philosophy needs to be discussed BEFORE stating whether this is “qualitative in nature”!!
 6. Data collection still unclear – same point as in previous meeting!!! How did you determine “reputable”??? Why are you calling this a “Literature Review”???
 7. Ethics section needed to be more specific – same point as in previous meeting!!
 8. Table is interesting, but you also need to provide evidence of how the thematic analysis and coding was done
 9. Conclusion needs to recap each objective.
 10. Tashfia has applied for a LA, will contact me when ready to discuss next FULL draft.
- Aims/Objectives seem to be mixed up! You should have ONE Research Aim, with 3-5 objectives to achieve that aim.
 - Page breaks before each chapter please.
 - Why is “Existence of Luxury Care Homes” in your conceptual framework (if you’re doing qualitative studies, dependent/independent variables aren’t really relevant here)
 - Make sure the Conceptual Framework is based on theory.
 - You need to explain exactly which sources you will use for literature – “...a lot of published and peer reviewed literature” lacks academic rigour.
 - Chapter 3 is about what you plan to do, not what you’ve already done. So the table in 3.6 actually belongs in chapter 4 (and label all tables please!)
 - You must describe how you did the coding and combined the codes into themes, with examples of the coding.
 - Conclusions need to recap EACH objective. In a separate subsection for each preferably.

Appendix B: Ethical Clearance

APPROVED BY SUPERVISOR

Email Approval :

Dear tashfia.shams,

Submission Ref: 41417

Please note that at the current time, all research projects involving interaction with human participants are required to use remote methods (e.g. videoconferencing) or postpone their research until the University lifts this restriction. Current guidance is available [here](#)

Following independent peer review of the above proposal*, I am pleased to inform you that **APPROVAL** has been granted on the basis of this proposal and subject to continued compliance with the University policies on ethics, informed consent, and any other policies applicable to your individual research. You should also have current Disclosure & Barring Service (DBS) clearance if your research involves working with children and/or vulnerable adults.

Appendix C: A Brief Reflection on the Dissertation and My Research

This reflective part of my writing offers in-depth insights into diverse aspects of luxury health care and how I managed to attain specific outcomes at the end of the course. Specifically, it includes an explanation about my understanding of several topics covered and developing existing professional skills and abilities acquired in my personal working experience. Besides, I believe that the knowledge I have obtained from this study will help me in working within the luxury industry environment. I was able to develop numerous skills such as teamwork skills, communication skills, and skills in terms of organisational and interpreting complex issues to do with luxury brand management. As a result, I have been able to develop new knowledge concerning novel contexts and environments, which makes it possible for me to interact with people from different cultural backgrounds, different languages, within academic, professional groups and social contexts. I will reflect and expound on these elements within this reflection. Importantly, I will illustrate on how all these courses has enabled me to exhibit my capabilities to work independently to ensure the success of my dissertation project.

I learned that completing a dissertation requires commitment and focus on methodologies, schedule, and goals. My study was based on a critical review of existing literature, which confirmed the usefulness of the internet since it helped in accessing information necessary to answer the research questions. I learned that one should follow certain tips, such as using the appropriate keywords to identify the appropriate source of information necessary to understand the topic. Besides, the internet provides access to sources from different parts of the world about the topic. The findings suggest a general increase in demand for luxury care for individuals undergoing end-of-life and palliative care.

However, in October, I experienced some personal challenges involving an accident which made me bedbound for 2 weeks and every day, was a challenge due to mobility issues. Finally, when the doctor saw me after 1 month of waiting with tremendous pain he recommended that a surgery was mandatory considering all the MRI reports. After hearing about the surgery, I was quite tensed and upset, wondering how would I manage everything and complete my dissertation at this stage of my life. I spoke to my course coordinator, who supported me throughout every decision I took. The fall adversely affected my lifestyle and the process of completing my dissertation. However, I am grateful that could complete the project on time. The experience helped me improve my time management skills, organisation, and ability to handle immense pressure mentally and physically. The pain from the accident could not allow me to read and led to slow progress during such stints. My surgery was scheduled on 18th of January (ACL Reconstruction and Meniscus Repair), where both legs were cut open as they could not get any strong Ligament from the right knee so they took it from the left knee and fixed my right leg. Due to COVID 19 restriction measure, I could not meet my family and friends as I came out of the theatre room and during the recovery phase. `

I learned that challenges should not place hurdle to pursuing one's passion, dedication, and heart. My Surgery was done privately and had the opportunity to experienced and to learn about the luxury niche. I will always cherish that particular night which I have spent after the surgery in the hospital which offered a personal experience that allowed me to appreciate and develop a passion for luxury care for chronic disease, elders, and patients under palliative care. As a care provider in the future, one of the essential goals is to improve the quality of life for people at end-of-life. My caregivers at the hospital were exceptional and, for one, made me forget about the absence of my family completely. I never felt the gap in my life because the care assistants were nice, compassionate, and served with empathy. Likewise, palliative care requires the enhancement of experiences to the taste of individuals because it is an emerging need in many communities in the world. It is a delicate part of life to ensure that people die with dignity.

My dissertation revealed that effective palliative care should result in minimal interference with a patient's life. For instance, daily chores and routines are essential aspects of life that improve the quality of existence. In most care institutions, the elders no longer undertake basic chores such as shopping and the food they eat. The elders lose touch with their culture, yet the resulting shock could create mental pressures. Therefore, the luxury care agency should introduce experiences that allow beneficiaries to take more control over their lives in those homes. The role of care assistance should help in medical emergencies, supervise patients, and educate the residents. Therefore, the knowledge gained through the dissertation and the care experienced during my time in the hospital enabled me to understand the luxury care market niche as a critical requirement to improve the quality of life. It is particularly necessary for people undergoing end-of-life decisions because it is shrouded with fear, confusion, and mental anguish. For that reason, I have developed a personal passion for working in luxury care to improve the quality of life when nearing death.